

Preregistration Supplement

Preregistrations AsPredicted.org #129594 (Vignette study: short reflections, purchase desire and purchase likelihood)

After conducting the study pilot:

- 1) We included a timer to measure time spend on the intervention as an additional variable.
- 2) We decided to include two attention checks as suggested by Prolific (see <https://researcher-help.prolific.co/hc/en-gb/articles/360009223553-Prolific-s-Attention-and-Comprehension-Check-Policy>) as participants completed the study quicker than we anticipated. These allow us to ensure high data quality by declining participants submissions who fail both attention checks. We decided for one instructional manipulation and one nonsensical item adapted from Prolific's examples.

Attention Checks

- Please select the right option '10 - Strongly agree' to show that you have read this sentence.
- I swim across the Atlantic Ocean to buy new clothes.

